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IMPLEMENTATION OF SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESPONSIBILITY (TJSL) AT PT PLN (PERSERO) SULUTTENGGGO DISTRIBUTION PARENT UNIT IN THE DIGITAL-BASED SMART HOME PROGRAM IN KAMPUNG BAHARI NUSANTARA DESA BUDO

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Abstract: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept that refers to the company's responsibility to the environment and society to provide benefits both internally for the company and externally for the community and the government. The purpose of this article is to find out how PT PLN (Persero) Suluttenggo Main Distribution Unit manages the CSR program. This case study involves the people of Budo Village. The logical framework method through the development of tourist areas and the development of MSEs. The results of the study show that the natural aspect of this program helps in increasing the promotion of Mangrove Forest tourism in Budo Village. From the economic aspect, this program greatly supports the economy of the community and the government of Budo Village through the maintenance of tourist attractions and the improvement of MSEs with the existence of Smart Houses. From the social aspect, this program is expected to increase the productivity and living standards of the people of Budo Village. Children can learn and relax at a leisurely pace without feeling overwhelmed. From the aspect of welfare, the first impact felt is the improvement of people's living standards, creating a smart community and always following technological developments. Second, the realization of the PLN Empowered Village Program "PLN Empowered Villages" based on SDG's.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Community Improvement Development, Smart Home Management

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Introduction

In ancient times, Budo Village was a forest. One day, a husband and wife came from Kaili Village. Over time, they had a white daughter named Budo. The name Budo Village was taken from this girl who came from Kaili. After some time, the parents and child left this place, and this place

then became plantation land for the people of Darunu Village who neighbor this area. Over time, this plantation turned into a village or hamlet called Dusun Budo.

Because initially the people here came from Darunu Village, in 1950, the number of residents in the village began to increase and they began to live independently. In 1965, a man named Yohanis Pinamangung, assisted by several friends, fought to separate this village from Darunu Village. Their goal is to stand alone and form one village consisting of two hamlets or hamlets called the Budo Village.

Figure 1. Budo Village
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Budo Village has a population of 914 people spread across 6 (six) hamlets or hamlets with a population distribution according to education level, namely:

Table 1. Population according to education level

No	Education	Man	Woman	Total
1	Elementary School/Primary School Graduate	199	190	389
2	Junior High School/Equivalent/Graduated High School	157	156	313
3	College	3	4	7

Source: Budo Village Government Office, 2024

OBJECTIVE

The objectives of implementing this program are:

1. Arouse and increase interest in reading so as to create an intelligent society.
2. Become a forum for community learning activities, especially for children with digital-based education from an early age.
3. Increase community insight, knowledge and skills.
4. Supporting the economy of the Budo Village community, especially in developing the Mangrove Tourism Area.
5. Can increase love, enthusiasm and ability to read.
6. As a forum for promoting PLN products and services.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Receiving Program Benefits

The beneficiaries of the Digital-Based Smart Home education assistance in Kampung Bahari Nusantara, Budo Village, are all residents of Budo Village as well as visitors who will visit the

mangrove tourism area of Budo Village. Why the people of Budo Village were chosen to receive this assistance was due to several things as follows:

1. Education level is dominated by elementary school graduates + 40%.
2. Budo Village is included as a buffer village for the Development of the Likupang Super Priority Tourism Destination Area.
3. Budo Village is one of the tourist villages that was visited directly by the Minister of Tourism and Creative Economy during the Indonesian Tourism Village Award event which was included in the top 50 best in 2022.

Program Initiation and Time Planning

Early in 2022, PLN carried out key stakeholder synergy with Lantamal VIII Manado, where Budo Village is a facility of Kampung Bahari Lantamal which requires special attention in the education sector. After going through the verification and survey stages from PLN UID Suluttenggo, the results are that the program is worthy of being designated as a Community Improvement Development (CID) Program for 2022. PLN's collaboration with related agencies/parties is:

1. Budo Village Government, District. North Minahasa.
2. Lantamal VIII Manado.
3. North Sulawesi Provincial Language Center.
4. Provincial Regional Library, North Sulawesi.
5. North Sulawesi Province Reading Ambassador.

Figure 2. Community Improvement Development (CID) Program

Source: Field research, 2024

Table 2. Community Improvement Development (CID) Activities

No	Activity	Time
1	Submission of Budo Village Proposal	May 05, 2022
2	Evaluation and Survey Stages	May 10, 2022
3	Dropping Program Budget	May 20, 2022
4	Budget Realization	May 27, 2022
5	On Progress work by collaborating with stakeholders (agencies/groups)	June July
6	Inauguration of Assistance	July 26, 2022
7	Monitoring and Evaluation	December 2022

Source: Field research, 2024

Implementation

The TJSL program includes a digital-based smart house in Kampung Bahari Nusantara, Budo Village, specifically directly in the Mangrove Area in the form of 1 (one) Smart House with an area of 7x9 meters which is directly on the coast of the Mangrove Area in Budo Village. This facility was built with a smart home visitor capacity of 50 – 75 people who can simultaneously use this smart home. This Smart House itself is equipped with supporting facilities that make people more enthusiastic about visiting the smart house. There, AC, Smart TV, Computer, Printer, bookshelves, beanbags, Edu PLN (Digital Library) and various reading books are provided. Simply put, this Smart

House can be a forum for people to increase their interest in reading, enrich the learning experience for the community, and can foster independent learning activities. Rumah Pintar is a platform/means for the community to help develop interest in reading and learning and also as a community supporter to promote the tourism sector around Rumah Pintar in the Mangrove Area. So this Smart Home assistance can be used by children and the general public.

Many activities are carried out there through visits from village residents or other visitors so that the general public can use the facilities for free. The management of the Smart House is directly handled by the Village Government and BUMDES. So the monitoring process in the use of facilities by the community is very clear, because the monitoring system is running.

Figure 3. Smart Home Management

Source: Field research, 2024

Table 3. Smart Home Management Activities

No	Activity	Time
1	PLN conducted a stakeholder visitation to Lantamal which is a key stakeholder to synergize existing programs together as part of joint support to improve the quality of education and the community's economy.	January 2022
2	Synergy activities are carried out through several TJSL activities also in the Kalinaun Likupang area.	February – April 2022
3	Direct coordination between PLN, Lantamal VIII and the Budo Village Government to jointly formulate targeted assistance for the Budo Village community.	April 2022
4	The "Digital Based Smart Home" Program was initiated with direct support from several parties.	May 2022
5	The program is realized according to the established budget and the Ceremony / Inauguration of the assistance is carried out.	June – July 2022
6	The process of utilizing assistance by the community by looking at the success of the program where one of the achievements of Budo Village was winning 1st place in ADWI based on Creative Digital.	August – November 2022
7	Monitoring and Evaluation with SROI.	December 2022

Source: Field research, 2024

Methods

Figure 4. Logical Framework for Increasing the Creative Economy of the Berdaya Budo Village Community through Development of Tourism Areas and Development of MSEs

Source: Field research, 2024

Results and Discussion

The results of implementing the Smart Home Reading Garden Program in Kampung Bahari Nusantara "Budo Village" for the people of Budo Village have provided very significant changes to their daily lives. These changes include:

1. The Budo Village community stated that the Smart Home Reading Park is very suitable for the needs of the community and visitors to Mangrove tourism, making it easier for the community to find the reference needs they want to look for.
2. The location chosen for the construction of the Smart PLN House is very appropriate, for long-term purposes, one of which is as a means of reading while on tour to enjoy the natural beaches and mangrove forests, visitors or local people can use the Smart House platform to broaden their knowledge.
3. People who almost all work as farmers, lacking knowledge, now no longer need to worry about increasing their insight or knowledge because in Budo Village they have access to reading, namely Rumah Pintar, as a digital means that always follows developments in science and technology and improves the level of education. community life.
4. Children can also learn independently, and can be a source of entertainment (recreation) because Rumah Pintar provides reading materials.
5. Budo Village was immediately visited by the Minister of Tourism and Creative Economy, Mr. Sandiaga Uno, who directly saw the sustainability of the program, one of which was digital-based at the assistance location, namely PLN Smart Home Assistance.

EVALUATION

As long as the Smart House has been built in Budo Village and is used by the community, no significant problems have been experienced. So far the Smart House has been used by the community for community learning activities and recreational reading for children, and all the equipment is still functioning well.

With the Aid Management System being directly handled by the Village Government and BUMDES, this is proven by the results of the IKM.

Table 4. Calculation of Community Satisfaction Index

No	SKM elements	Σ	NRR	Weighted NRR
1	Product Conformity	1,034	3.42	0.31
2	Product quality	1,033	3.42	0.31
3	Method of Completion	1,004	3.32	0.30
4	Location Selection	1,104	3.66	0.33
5	Management Suitability	1,096	3.63	0.33
6	Implementing Competency	1,023	3.39	0.31
7	Implementing Behavior	1,052	3.48	0.32
8	Facilities and Infrastructure	1,062	3.52	0.32
9	Handling Complaints, Suggestions and Feedback	1,183	3.92	0.36
10	Program Sustainability	1,201	3.98	0.36
11	Benefit	1,198	3.97	0.36
		11,990	39.70	
	NI			3.61
	WEIGHT	0.091		
	VIN	90.2318		

Source: Field research, 2024

By measuring the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM), the total index obtained from the average service unit SME is 90.23. With these figures, it can be concluded that TJSL services in Budo Village are at quality level (x): A with performance (y): Very Good.

RESULTS AND IMPACT

The results and impact of the Smart Home Reading Park program in Kampung Bahari Nusantara "Budo Village" if viewed from a sustainability compass, the results are as follows:

1. Nature

Viewed from the Nature aspect, this program helps increase the promotion of Mangrove Forest tourism, namely Budo Village - Mangrove Forest.

2. Economy (Economy)

From an economic aspect, this program really helps the economy of the community / government of Budo Village in maintaining tourist attractions by increasing the MSEs through the presence of Smart Homes.

3. Social (Social)

From the Social aspect, it is hoped that this program can increase the productivity and standard of living of the people of Budo Village. Children can learn and have recreation in a relaxed manner without having any burdens.

4. Wellbeing (Welfare)

In terms of the Wellbeing aspect, the impacts felt are:

- 1) Improving the standard of living of the community so as to create a society that is intelligent and always follows technological developments.
- 2) Realization of the PLN Empowered Village Program "PLN Empowered Villages" based on SDG's.

Scoring and SROI Calculation

The main essence of scoring and calculating SROI as stated previously is to measure the business "return" from social activities carried out by PT PLN (Persero). On this occasion, an assessment was carried out with the results of calculating the value of the evaluative impacts on the education assistance program in Kampung Bahari Nusantara which is equipped with a Smart Home Reading Park, namely:

1. Input: 150,000,000
2. Outcome: 720,000,000
3. Attribution (10%) : 648,000,000
4. Present Value (r = 5.5): 612,360,000
5. SROI Ratio: 4.082

Based on the calculation results, an SROI Ratio of 4.082 is obtained, meaning that every investment of IDR 1,- gets an impact or benefit worth IDR. 4,082,-. When viewed from a socio-economic perspective, the education assistance program in Indonesian maritime villages equipped with smart home reading gardens can be said to be very feasible and successful.

The beneficial impact of the program is proven by the number of visitors to school children after the presence of the Digital-based Smart House in Kampung Bahari Nusantara "Budo Village" which can be seen in the following table:

Figure 5. Number of School Children Visitors

Source: Field research, 2024

Figure 6. Number of Community Visitors

Source: Field research, 2024

Meanwhile, the local community uses the Smart House as a place to get information through reading books, computer equipment and smart TVs, as well as the Digital Library through EduPLN.

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